

ISic1073

I.Sicily inscription 1073

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Modica

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140553

1. . . ΝΙΓΕΝ έτελ[εύ]τ[η]σεν
2. πρò ι' καλ[α]ν[δ]ών Φρεβαρί-
3. ων ²⁶Φεβρουαρίων²⁶ ήμέρα ΡΕΝΙΙΙΟΙC μνησθ[ή] αύ-
4. τ [ής] {²⁷αύτ [οϋ]}²⁷ #⁷ ó κύριος.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492700

EDCS 39102228

PHI 140553

Bibliography

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